

**PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE
DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE SOCIAL WORKERS BASED ON
ADVANCED FOREIGN EXPERIENCES**

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Abstract Abstract: the scientific novelty of our research is the further increase of the essence of professional competence, the further increase in demand, the optimal way of forming this pedagogical quality in future specialists based on the results of scientific researches that serve to justify its necessity for training competitive highly qualified specialists.

Key words: social workers, professional competence, communicative, informational, intellectual, theoretical competence model,

INTRODUCTION

Today, the world community is undergoing valuable changes in all areas of life, which in turn requires a new approach to the formation of a future professional. What is different for our time is the changes in the quality of education - its orientation, purpose, content - all of them consider the future specialist's qualities such as "free development of a person", creative initiative, independence of education, competitiveness, mobility. holds These acquired changes, in their own way, represent the process of changing the educational paradigm.

The main goal of studying the professional competence of specialists of educational institutions is the role of professional competence of specialists in the educational process and knowledge about competence, qualities of professional competence, self-development, self-management. is to help them acquire a deeper formation, high national communication techniques and culture, and to ensure that they have a mature qualification in professional competence. Because today's personnel is one of the main participants of the fundamental changes taking place in our life, he is a person who is mature in all respects, has deep knowledge, has specialist skills and abilities loyal to his country and people, and knows well his duties in society and profession.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The processes of assimilation in world civilization include modernization and diversification of educational services based on the integration of research-education-production, development of human-specialist capital, increase of creative activity of specialists, as well as meta-competencies that allow them to

quickly adapt to changing trends in the labor market (soft skills) as the strategic direction of innovation-driven economy. In particular, the "Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2030"[1], adopted at the 70th anniversary session of the United Nations General Assembly, the International Education Forum's Incheon Declaration, development of personnel competence at all levels of education[2], On the basis of the integration of formal, non-formal and informal education, systematic work is being carried out to ensure the synergetic effect of continuous improvement of professional skills [3].

Changes in the field of educational goals in our country, as in the whole world, correspond to global issues aimed at ensuring the entry of a person into the social world. In particular, in the documents of the improvement of the educational system, the competent approach is announced as an important conceptual condition for updating the educational content. To implement a competent approach in the educational system, it is necessary to train and retrain social work staff who will have the ability to apply their basic competence in real life and professional practice. Competent approach is aimed at forming social, communicative, informational, professional and other personal qualities of the learner, and allows almost complete implementation of modern socio-economic conditions. This approach is based on the concept of competences, such as the formation of the personality of learners on the basis of the ability to fully educate them and solve important practical tasks [4].

The goal of the competent approach is to ensure the quality of education. The analysis of the published documents on the problems of improving the educational system shows that competence and competence are considered as the main units in updating the educational content.

First of all, we should emphasize that the competence orientation of education was formed in the 1970s in America. The currently considered concepts of "competence" and "competence" were founded at that time and are interpreted as "a personal and intellectual experience based on a person's knowledge, defined in the activities of his social professional life" [5]. In the 1970s, it also appeared in many Western European countries, and competence defined a new direction of vocational education. The term "competence" means not only the acquisition of individual, technical or experiential knowledge and skills, but also the set of abilities and skills that can be the basis for the further development of a person. However, this idea is expressed differently in all European countries. A number of well-known psychologists (Chris Argiris, Richard E. Boyatzis, George O. Clamp, Jr. James, M. Lyle, Jr. Spencer) worked on the topic of professional

competence. They studied a wide range of competencies in their research, including professional competencies, managerial competencies, communication competencies, and employee performance[6].

In Germany, since the 1980s, "vocational competence" has been used to describe the goal to be achieved through basic vocational education. This goal consists of a combination of interpersonal skills, technical complex and general knowledge, which allowed the graduate to continue working in various workplaces of the organization. This general qualification cannot remain unchanged, it must be developed, because the demands and conditions of the world of work also change for the benefit of the individual and society.

In Great Britain, a system known as "core competencies" is actively used. Core competencies are important specific competencies that are used in learning in everyday life.

Core competencies perform 3 functions:

- 1) They help students learn.
- 2) Employees are able to meet the demands of employers in short order.
- 3) Helps to achieve success in life.

Also, key competencies:

1. Competencies reinforced by numbers - the ability to enter numerical data, perform calculations, and present final conclusions.
2. Communication - the ability to listen, read, summarize and receive information.
3. Information technologies - presentation of information in various forms such as text, numbers, diagrams.
4. Ability to manage independent education and independent presentation - management of employees.
5. Working with people - the ability to work with people in the planning and implementation of activities in a team with a common goal [7].

Basic competencies develop throughout the entire activity, for example, during the implementation of vocational training programs, in the performance of labor obligations, and in receiving various forms of education.

The famous English psychologist J. Raven (Dj. Raven) proposed a theoretical model of competence and, at the same time, new directions in its assessment. According to Raven, competence is a limited set of specialized knowledge, special abilities, ways of thinking, and a sense of responsibility for one's actions needed to perform a specific task effectively. Raven talks about what he calls "superior competencies." High competencies require high initiative from people,

the ability to take the initiative in organizing human activities to achieve their goals, social consequences of their actions and commitment. First of all, it is determined what a person wants to do, and then it is determined what components of competence he demonstrates in this activity. The Raven Competency Model is a unique "map" of competency areas composed of motivation, willpower, and performance components.

Leboter developed and systematized a theory called "competence engineering". According to Leboter, competence is a set of knowledge, skills, abilities, as well as the use of past and new experience in any activity. Competence is the ability to perform a task effectively, to act in accordance with the norms used in a particular profession.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Let's take a look at the main competencies listed in the content of the European secondary education project:

Education:

- ability to use experience;
- organizing and placing the interdependence of acquired knowledge;
- organizing the use of personal knowledge;
- ability to solve problems;
- engage in education according to one's own will.

Research:

- searching for various information;
- ask others;
- expert advice;
- receiving information;
- to be able to work with documents and classify them.

Account:

- Establishing the relationship between past and present events;
- a critical approach to one or another aspect of the community development process;
- overcoming difficulties;
- to take one's own position in debates and have a personal opinion;
- paying attention to the important political and environmental aspects of the educational process;
- assessment of social skills related to health and environment;
- evaluation of masterpieces of art and literature.

Collaborate:

- teamwork and cooperation;
- ability to make decisions;
- the ability to resolve disputes and disagreements;
- agreement;
- execution of contracts;
- introduction to the project;
- sense of responsibility;
- Join and contribute to the group and team;
- expressing solidarity;
- being able to organize one's own work;
- ability to work with computing devices.

Get used to it:

- ability to use new information and communication technologies;
- show conciseness in frequently changing conditions;
- show your strength and perseverance against difficulties;
- making new decisions.

Thus, it can be said that competence is a limited special knowledge, special abilities that cover ways of thinking and a sense of responsibility for one's actions, necessary for the effective performance of a specific task. As a result, in all areas of literacy education, attention is paid to the individual's experience, his active position, the level of readiness for activity, and the needs of the socio-cultural community.

Scientists and practitioners who have conducted a number of researches on the development of professional competence in young personnel in the higher education system regularly correct or update the sequence system (taxonomy of objectives) of educational goals, the ways to achieve professional competence development, improvement, the results of the activities of young personnel who emphasized the effect of increasing efficiency. It was created by the American scientist B. Bloom (published "Taxonomy" (Part I) in 1956). The creation of the affective field of the taxonomy of pedagogical goals by D. Kratvol and other scientists; cognitive field (cognitive field) - from remembering and retelling the material that has been read, to fully understanding the acquired knowledge and combining it with previously learned ideas, methods and methods of action imagination; it is stated that it includes solving problems up to the acquisition of knowledge.

The issue of effective and widespread use of "competence" in education is in the general sense of the term "competence" recognized by the great philosopher,

scientist, linguist, theorist, political publicist, professor of the University of Massachusetts, American Avram Noam Chomsky (1965). the content gained substance. His views were included in the list of concepts such as "training", "competence", "ability", "skill" for the first time from the concept of "competence" at the symposium held in Bern in 1996 under the program of the Council of Europe. . Also, in 1999, the ministers of education of developed European countries paid a lot of attention to the issue of "competent approach" as a conceptual basis of educational reforms in the Bologna Declaration [8].

A number of scientific results have been achieved through research conducted in the world on the development of didactic support for competent training of students. Among them: methods and methods of competence assessment have been developed (the University of Chicago); an integrative model of professional competence requiring a five-step evaluation was developed (University of Sheffield); Validation and recognition of competencies and qualifications as a common goal and primary task at the level of European education is conceptually based (University of Tours); Three-level competency indicators are defined and recommended, which allow for a better understanding of educational outcomes and to increase the openness of professions (University of Twente); In order to clarify the concept of "professional competence", two main approaches are based: the specific activity of a person and the formation of a person as a professional [9].

Among the most developed countries of the world, America, Germany, France, Brazil, Spain, Finland, Russia and other countries have carried out considerable scientific work on the theory of competence and competence in education, in particular, the system of development of the main components of the competence approach. comments are made. For example, the American linguist M. Chomsky first used the term "competence" in his works in the middle of the 20th century and defined it as "the ability of a person to perform an activity"[10].

As we mentioned above, the concept of competence is analyzed in the sources based on different interpretations. In particular, according to T.S. Zelenetskaya, competence is the integral characteristics of a person that arise in the process of education and socialization and are manifested in his knowledge, experience-based general abilities, effective organization of activities, focused on his independent and effective participation in activities [11].

Researcher D.Yermakov evaluates competence as an opportunity to provide holistic personal education characterized by the following characteristics:

- operativeness and mobility of knowledge, the ability to apply and combine each specific situation, taking into account its various aspects;
- willingness to make a decision, the ability to choose a convenient method in the given situation;
- communicative ability, ability to establish a strong relationship with other persons within the scope of activity;
- the ability to develop one's own creative abilities, the desire to master new aspects related to certain activities.

CONCLUSION

The Finnish scientist G. Garfinkel, who put forward the idea that competence is a concept that shows a personal attitude towards this type of activity in addition to having a certain ability, comments on this concept in his scientific works. He understands competence as a person's knowledge, skills and experiences, social-professional, i.e. suitability for the professional position he occupies in society, ability to perform his duties and solve problems related to him. From its definition, it can be concluded that competence is a person's possession of certain knowledge and skills and is ready to work effectively in this or that situation

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